

THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Annotation: Artificial intelligence (AI) is bringing significant changes to the field of education, especially in the methods of language learning. Through adaptive systems, personalized feedback, and natural language processing (NLP) tools, AI offers new opportunities for students and teachers to improve the learning process.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Language Learning, Education Technology, Personalized Learning, Natural Language Processing, Creativity.

Annotatsiya: Sun'iy intellekt (SI) ta'lim sohasida, ayniqsa, tillarni o'rganish usullarida katta o'zgarishlar qilmoqda. Moslashuvchan tizimlar, shaxsiylashtirilgan fikr-mulohazalar va tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash (NLP) vositalari orqali SI o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilarga o'quv jarayonini yaxshilash uchun yangi imkoniyatlar taqdim etmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: Sun'iy intellekt, Til o'rganish, Ta'lim texnologiyasi, Shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish, Tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash, Ijodkorlik.

Аннотация: Искусственный интеллект (ИИ) вносит значительные изменения в сферу образования, особенно в методы изучения языков. Благодаря адаптивным системам, персонализированной обратной связи и инструментам обработки естественного языка (NLP), ИИ предоставляет учащимся и преподавателям новые возможности для улучшения учебного процесса.

Ключевые слова: Искусственный интеллект, Изучение языков, Образовательные технологии, Персонализированное обучение, Обработка естественного языка, Креативность.

In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) has started to play an important role in education. It helps in many ways, such as grading and giving students personal support. Language learning has especially improved with AI because of its ability to understand and use natural language. At the same time, there are also questions about how this technology affects teaching, creativity, and real human communication. This paper looks at both the positive and negative effects of AI in language learning. It uses examples from research and expert opinions to

understand how AI is changing the way people learn languages. Researchers at NYU studied how AI can learn language in a similar way to small children. They used videos from toddlers to train the AI, and found that it could learn patterns by watching and listening, just like humans do. Another example is Pearson, a major education company, which uses AI to give students feedback, guide their learning, and help them with speaking skills. These tools make learning more personal and flexible. However, not everyone agrees that AI is always good. John Warner, in his book *More Than Words*, says AI can't replace human creativity. He believes AI writing often sounds correct but feels empty and lacks a personal touch, which is very important in real language use. However, AI offers many helpful features for language learners like this parts:

AI can adjust to a student's level and needs making learning more effective because students can learn new knowledges anytime in anywhere, also it is free to use. Apps like Grammarly correct mistakes right away, so students can improve quickly and effectively without any challenges because here everything understandable for any level students. AI chatbots help learners practice conversations and improve their speaking skill fast and easily in learning process. AI can improve language learning in many ways, but it can also cause problems if not used properly. The NYU and Pearson examples show how AI can support learning, while Warner reminds us not to forget about the value of human thinking and creativity. A balanced approach is important. AI should help the learning process, but not take over completely. Teachers and students need to use it wisely, combining technology with real human interaction and personal expression.

Conclusion. Artificial intelligence is clearly changing how people learn languages. It offers useful benefits like faster learning, personal support, and easier access to education around the world. Still, there are some important concerns. If students and teachers rely too much on AI, it may reduce real communication, creativity, and human connection. In the future, it is important to find a balance between using new technology and keeping traditional teaching methods. AI should help and support language learning, not replace the valuable parts of human interaction. Only with this balance can AI truly be helpful in language education.

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